

1 **Evidence describing a chemotherapeutic regimen to treat CNS disease in HER2+ breast cancer.**

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
4 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
5 East Islip, NY USA 11730

6 This regimen is designed for patients with HER2+ breast cancer that have developed metastasis to the
7 central nervous system (brain). The complete regimen includes targeted and neoadjuvant agents, all of
8 which have been FDA-approved. The complete regimen has not yet been tested or evaluated for use in
9 humans. The regimen described here includes a platinum agent, a folate inhibitor, an escalated dose of a
10 CDK4/6 inhibitor (-ciclib), pembrolizumab, bevacizumab, neratinib, capecitabine, and doxorubicin. A
11 secondary formulation contains, in addition to the agents in the described regimen, an EGFR inhibitor and
12 an inhibitor of the MET tyrosine kinase.

13 **Discussion**

14 Platinum agent: cisplatin, carboplatin or oxaliplatin.

15 Platinum agents are basic elements in multiple chemotherapeutic regimens; cisplatin, carboplatin and
16 oxaliplatin have some level of CNS penetration capacity.

17 Folate inhibitor (antimetabolite): 5-FU, pemetrexed, or pralatrexate.

18 The metastatic patient should be assumed to possess an active disease process with peripheral tumor
19 burden that will continue to support dissemination; despite described inability to penetrate the CNS, 5-FU
20 is effective in treating disease burden in the periphery in patients with metastatic disease, of hematopoietic
21 or solid tissue origin.

22 CDK4/6 inhibitors: abemaciclib, palbociclib, or ribociclib.

23 The dose of CDK4/6 inhibitor utilized in the clinic varies based on whether the patient is receiving the
24 -ciclib as an adjunctive during endocrine therapy or for the treatment of metastatic disease. A higher dose
25 of the CDK4/6 inhibitor is indicated for patients treated for metastatic disease.

26 Immunotherapy: pembrolizumab

27 Pembrolizumab (Keytruda) has some level of limited efficacy in treating metastatic disease and penetrates
28 the CNS. Immunotherapies like pembrolizumab engage the B7-CTLA4 system at the immunologic
synapse to "invigorate" the immune system and favor cytolytic activity by lymphocytes.

Anti-angiogenic: bevacizumab

Angiogenic processes should be limited in active metastatic disease. Bevacizumab has some level of
limited efficacy in prolonging survival outcomes in patients with CNS metastasis.

Standard CNS MBC treatment in HER2+ disease: neratinib and capecitabine

HER2+ disease that has metastasized to the brain requires a CNS penetrant HER2-targeting agent; this is
essentially limited to neratinib (or tucatinib or an older related agent, lapatinib). Capecitabine, an
antimetabolite, is one of few agents demonstrated to possess some level of efficacy in the CNS in HER2+
brain metastasis.

1 Anthracycline: doxorubicin

2
3 EGFR and MET inhibition

4 A second design for this experimental regimen additionally contains small molecule inhibitors for EGFR
5 (*ERBB1/HER1*), gefitinib or erlotinib, and MET (*HGFR*), cabozantinib or crizotinib. This design is based
6 on study of the largest differences transcriptome-wide between metastasis to the lung and to the brain in
7 women with HER2+ breast cancer.

8
9 **Additional notes**

10 Monotherapy with trastuzumab should be considered dangerous, when considering a metastasis-prone
11 population.

12 In certain blood cancers, CNS disease was prevalent (at a rate of 75% CNS relapse in childhood ALL)
13 before CNS prophylaxis was established and regularly practiced (Hill and Owen, 2006); one hematologic
14 protocol utilizes high-dose (5-8g/m²) intrathecal (IT) and intravenous (IV) methotrexate for CNS
15 prophylaxis.

16 Anthracyclines (doxorubicin and daunorubicin) are cardiotoxic.

17 Deep vein thrombosis and other thrombotic events has been reported to occur at a higher rate in patients
18 receiving CDK4/6 inhibitors, but a thorough study establishing a standard rate of cancer-associated
19 thrombosis (CAT) in patients with breast cancer, how this rate differs in patients treated with endocrine
20 therapy (where treatment with tamoxifen has been described to result in an increased rate of DVT), and
21 the rate of DVT in patients treated with CDK4/6 inhibitors differs from that of a patient population
22 manifesting CAT and widely treated with tamoxifen is not known; it is described as higher.

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